

Thermo-energy and environmental evaluation in the vertical envelope of high-rise buildings: a case study in Tucumán, Argentina

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ABSTRACT

The following work studies the environmental impact in the initial and use stages, produced by the construction materials most used in high-rise building's exterior vertical envelope in the Metropolitan Area of Tucumán, Argentina. The results expose the high energy values consumed by the manufacture, transport and assembly of the materials as well as deficiencies in the hygrothermal behavior of the built envelope, and therefore large carbon equivalent emissions. In this sense, a construction solution with low environmental impact is proposed for its thermal rehabilitation. It concludes on the importance of improving the hygrothermal properties of the envelope through materials and construction systems with low environmental impact.

KEYWORDS

Environmental impact; Architectural envelope; Hygro-thermal behavior.

INTRODUCTION

The building sector is responsible for 40% of energy consumption and 36% of anthropogenic origin greenhouse gas emissions worldwide (Rivero Camacho, et.al. 2018). In Argentina, as Kuchen and Kozak (2020) say, 37% of energy consumption is building sector responsibility, with air conditioning the most representative item. These percentages include the energy consumed for the transport and manufacture of the construction element, which is defined as embodied energy (Quispe Gamboa, 2016) and the energy expenditure for the air conditioning of the buildings in the use stage.

If we focus on the environmental impact produced by the most used construction materials, we find cement, steel, ceramics and glass. Ceramic is a material made from the firing of clay; therefore, it generates an environmental imbalance from the process of extracting the raw material. López and Salazar (2016), carried out a study on the extraction of clay, they determined that the environmental alteration that produces the extraction of this mineral generates impacts on the biotic, abiotic, social and cultural environments. In addition, it should be noted that the brick manufacturing process has become an ecological problem due to the type of fuel used for firing, which generates a large amount of GHG into the atmosphere (Restrepo-Zapata and Cadavid-Restrepo, 2019). The reinforced concrete is essentially made up of three elements: aggregates, cement and steel, it causes soil erosion due to the extraction of aggregates and, in addition, around 5% of CO₂ emissions, the main gas that produces the greenhouse effect and climate change. (Gessa and Sancha, 2016). As for steel, its manufacturing process is responsible for more than 4% of global CO₂ emissions (Rueda, 2018).

On the other hand, if we look at the exterior vertical enclosures materials, they infer a 50% on the building's climatization energetic waste (Venhaus-Held, Alías & Jacobo, 2017). To regulate and control the thermal comfort of a building in a hot humid climate, the building envelope is the most important design parameter. Sadinesi, Madala and Boehm (2011), consider that the walls make up the predominant fraction of the architectural envelope, providing thermal and acoustic comfort, and it is the element that makes the greatest aesthetic contribution to the construction. In this sense, the

adequate design of the envelope is essential (González Vásquez and Molina-Prieto, 2017), both of a building rehabilitation and a new project in order to achieve almost zero energy and carbon buildings.

Based on the above, this research attempts to answer the following questions. How to reduce energy costs and carbon equivalent emissions in an existing building? What materials and construction systems are suitable for a thermo-energy rehabilitation? A 12-story high-rise building in the Metropolitan Area of Tucumán (AMET) is taken as a case study. It is the prototype of the most used high-rise building in the urban geometry of the conglomerate and with a high incidence of the number of m² built for the materialization of its envelope. In this sense, it is important to determine the Accumulated Energy (AE) and Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions both in its initial stages (manufacturing, transportation and assembly on site) and in the stage of use. And, to this end, to propose possible solutions that allow a low environmental impact and the energy and carbon reduction equivalent in its use. And, to this end, propose possible solutions that allow a low environmental impact and the energy and carbon reduction equivalent in its use.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology has 3 stages. In the first one, the geographical area where the building under study is located, its functional and technical-constructive typology are characterized. In a second stage, the values of the existing walls' hygrothermal behavior are determined using data from previous studies. In addition, the values of the equivalent CO₂ emissions and energy consumption produced by the manufacture of the envelope materials are shown. For this, the normalized data of emissions and energy consumption per Kg of material in relation to the total Kg of material present in the building vertical envelope are used. And finally, in the third stage, the type of constructive resolution of low environmental impact that is proposed for energy rehabilitation and its hygrothermal and environmental characteristics are characterized.

RESULTS

First stage

Characterization of the geographical area where it is located

The unit of analysis studied in this paper is located in the Metropolitan Area of Tucumán, Argentina. The climatic conditions demand the application of bioclimatic strategies for both the hot and cold periods. It is characterized by a summer with maximum average temperatures above 30 °C and in winter minimum average temperatures below 10 °C, according to IRAM 11603. According to a study carried out using the software Climate consultant, it is determined that in a typical year there are 37.2% of comfort hours, 31.9% of cold hours and 30.9% of hot hours. Regarding the need for shading, 32.9% of shading hours are required in a typical year, between 10:00 a.m. and 19:00 p.m.

Study case description

The study case is a housing high rise building, located in the central area from San Miguel de Tucumán city, in Argentina. It is configured as a building between party walls, with a main axis in an east-west direction and its main faces open to those orientations (fig. 1). It presents internal patios towards which openings are located. The north and south orientations configured the party walls, which are completely blind.

Figure 1. Planimetry of the study case. Source: Own elaboration based on municipal cadastre office.

As for its materialization, the building is resolved with a load-bearing structure of reinforced concrete, that is, point load elements (columns) and linear (partitions), the mezzanines and the roof, are resolved with a reinforced concrete slab. This structure responds to the seismic-resistant regulations in force for seismic zone 2, in Argentina, according to INPRES-CIRSOC (2005). The exterior vertical envelope is non-bearing hollow ceramic brick 0.18 m thickness, plastered on both sides. The windows are resolved entirely in wood (frame and leaf), with simple 4 mm glass. The roof is made of solid reinforced concrete slab, with waterproof insulation on its outer face.

Nowadays, in San Miguel de Tucumán, in the Metropolitan Area of Tucumán, multiple high-rise buildings are observed where the same exterior wall construction technique is used. Although, according to IRAM 11603 (2012), for the zone under study, the roof is the most important part in terms of thermal performance, in the study case, the vertical envelope is more relevant since its specific surface is more than ten times higher than that of the roof (Table 1).

Table 1. Specific area of the building envelope. Source: self made.

	Total area m ²	building volume m ³	Specific area m ² /m ³
Vertical envelope	3.484	10.833,90	0,32
Roof	323,40		0,029

Second stage

Vertical envelope environmental impact in the initial stage of the life cycle

As shown in previous paragraphs, the materialization of the high-rise buildings walls in the Metropolitan Area of Tucumán is solved with a wet construction system, with a reinforced concrete punctual structure and non-bearing ceramic walls. To know the environmental impact of the manufacturing stage of the materials that make up the vertical envelope, values are used from the database of the Institute of Construction Technology of Catalonia (ITeC), BEDEC PR/PCT. On the one hand, values are used for the GHG emissions generated in the manufacturing and transportation process. These are quantified in Kg of CO₂ equivalent, based on the global warming potential, according to the life cycle analysis methodology (IRAM series 14.000). This indicator refers to the warming effect produced today by an instantaneous release of 1kg of a greenhouse gas, compared to that caused by CO₂ (Greenfacts, 2001). On the other hand, values are taken and the energy consumption of primary energy in MJ, in the manufacturing stage of these materials is studied. This indicator is relevant in terms of environmental impact, since the materials that provide the energy required in these processes generate significant amounts of toxic waste, as well as physical alterations

to the natural environment in which the energy is produced (Argüello Méndez and Cuchí Burgos, 2008).

This table shows the values of GHG and embodied energy for the manufacture and transportation process, what is called stage A1-A3 in the methodology LCA (Life Cycle Assessment), of the construction materials that make up the walls of the building.

Table 3-2. GHG and Embodied Energy of the vertical envelope. Source: self-made.

Element	Material	Amount Kg	Energy cost MJ/Kg	Energy cost MJ	CO ₂ Emission Kg/Kg	CO ₂ Emission Kg
Masonry	Ceramic	268.560	2,321	623.327,76	0,18	48.340,80
	Cement	9.109	4,360	39.715,24	0,41	3.743,69
Reinforced concrete	Cement	79.010	4,360	344.483,60	0,41	3.239
	Steel	31.604	35,000	1,106,140	2,80	88.941

It is observed that the highest GHG emissions from the vertical envelope are the responsibility of the steel contained in the reinforced concrete skeleton structure. In second place is the ceramic brick, because of the amount of it present in the building envelope. The environmental impact produced by cement is not negligible, but it is considerably lower than the one produced by brick and steel for the analyzed case.

As for the building windows , it is resolved entirely with wood (frame and sheet), which, according to the Secretary of Environment and Sustainable Development (2016) represents a 78% reduction in the impact of climate change, compared to the windows sheet metal or PVC.

Vertical envelope environmental impact in the use stage from its life cycle.

The ceramic hollow brick constructive solution of 0.18 m plastered on both sides, has little thermal insulation $k= 1.73 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ (Fernández, Garzón, 2020). As Bustamante, et al (2005) says the thermal insulation standards of hollow ceramic brick are considered precarious, meeting the needs for optimal use in buildings, as well as thermal protection requirements. As for the reinforced concrete, it has a thermal transmittance coefficient 88.3% higher than the brick, being $k= 3.26 \text{ w/m}^2\text{K}$.

Regarding the risks of condemnation, previous studies (Fernández Garzón, 2020) determined that both construction elements present risks of interstitial condensation, while concrete also presents risks of surface condensation. Condensation humidity is produced from vapor-laden air masses inside a building that, at contact with cold surfaces, reduce their temperature to the dew point (Martínez, Sarmiento and Urquieta, 2005). This causes formation to mold which causes health problems and discomfort in people due to the appearance of germs that contaminate the environment. In addition, they favor pathological processes such as efflorescence on walls and floors, corrosion and rotting of metallic and wooden elements, respectively, and the decrease in the thermal insulation of the envelope.

Under this scenario, there is evidence of a deficit in the hygrothermal comfort of the interior space and requires the use of active thermo-mechanical air conditioning systems supplied with non-renewable energy from the existing electrical distribution network. In this sense, it is determined through similar studies (Saez et al., 2021) that if a split-type inverter air conditioner is used for each habitable room in the building, with energy efficiency level A and nominal capacity of 9.5 Kw, there is a consumption of 17,531.8 Kwh per year and consequently, 8,753.63 Kg CO₂ equivalent per year. For this purpose, if the stage of use of the building is considered to be 70 years, these figures amount to 2,103,816 Kwh and 612,754.8 Kg CO₂ equivalents.

Third stage

Rehabilitation proposal from the exterior vertical envelope

Given the thermal-energy and environmental inefficiency of the vertical envelope used in the building in question it is proposed the incorporation of a thermal insulator on the inner face, due to the risk of condensation on the inner layers (figure 2). It is intended to reduce the k and achieve the verification of thermal bridges. The proposal consists of placing a 0.05 m layer of mineral rock wool towards the interior and a layer of cardboard plasterboard. The resistant structure of said solution will be carried out with 2x2” pine wood strips.

Figure 2. Original case wall and proposed rehabilitation wall. Source: Own elaboration.

Environmental impact from the rehabilitation proposal

The materials proposed for rehabilitation are considered low impact. On the one hand, wood is the only construction material with a negative carbon balance, since the CO₂ stored in the trees is greater than the emissions associated with harvesting, transportation, and processing (Hernández and Elgueta, 2020). It has a low energy cost, compared to the materials that make up the current vertical envelope of the building. Wood entails an energy consumption in its elaboration and installation process of 2.10 MJ/Kg and emissions of 0.06 Kg of CO₂/Kg (Argüello Méndez and Cuchi Burgos, 2008). In this last consideration, the emissions from its manufacturing process are studied and the CO₂ absorption of the trees is not taken into account.

On the other hand, if it is taken into account that many existing insulating materials are manufactured with petrochemical products (Asdrubali et al., 2015), the use of rock mineral wool is proposed, as it is considered a material that presents a process of less environmentally damaging manufacturing than other insulators (Belando and Lopez-Mesa, 2010). In this sense, it coincides with what was stated by Álvarez and Ripoll Meyer (2018) that the three pillars of sustainability must be taken into account when choosing a construction material. That is to say, reduction of the environmental impact, that is economically viable and that guarantees the quality of life of the living beings that intervene throughout their entire life cycle.

Thermal properties of the proposal

From the point of view of thermal insulation, significant improvements in thermal transmittance are observed. After the insulation proposal is made, compliance with thermal bridges of the walls is verified, since in its original version it is not verified. A ratio of 1.11 is obtained between the k of the concrete and the brick wall (both with mineral wool and plasterboard). This value indicates that the thermal bridge verifies with the norm. To assess the risks of condensation, the same methodology is used as in the original wall, through the C-RC calculator. With the proposed solution, it is possible to

completely eliminate all types of condensation risk for the most critical climatic situation, absolute minimum temperature. To this end, through this type of constructive resolutions for rehabilitation, the energy consumed for air conditioning can be reduced by 30% and in direct relation to GHG emissions (Saez et al., 2021).

CONCLUSION

Faced with the high energy consumption and CO₂ emissions generated by the building sector, the need arises to propose more sustainable construction solutions. They refer to both the construction stage and the useful life of the buildings, emphasizing thermal conditioning. The unit of analysis corresponds to a typical constructive solution of high-rise buildings present in the AMET. Likewise, this type of building continues to be reproduced, not only in high-density areas of the city but also in other low-density residential areas, which would indicate the proliferation of the model today and its continuity in the coming years. In the study case, an exterior vertical envelope without sustainability criteria is evidenced. On the one hand, their thermal properties are deficient, since they do not comply with local regulations, presenting low levels of hygrothermal comfort, as well as thermal bridges and condensation risks. On the other hand, the materials that make up the vertical envelope have a high environmental impact in their production process, represented by high energy consumption and GHG emissions. Since the vertical envelope is the main surface component of the envelope of a high-rise building, and since the analyzed masonry is constituted as a typical AMET solution, a lack of sustainability criteria is evident in the construction practice and in the current real estate market. For this reason, the work allows us to reflect on the need to propose new construction materials with less environmental impact, both to materialize future buildings, as well as to be implemented in thermal rehabilitation solutions.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.